

1 **Beneficial effects of reduced tillage and green manure on soil aggregation and**
2 **stabilization of organic carbon in a Mediterranean agroecosystem.**

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9 Abstract

10 Mediterranean semiarid agroecosystems need the implementation of sustainable land
11 management (SLM) practices in order to maintain acceptable levels of soil organic matter (SOM).
12 The application of SLM practices helps to maintain soil structure and physical-chemical protection
13 of soil organic carbon (SOC), hence improving soil carbon sequestration and mitigating CO₂
14 emissions to the atmosphere. In an organic, rain-fed almond (*Prunus dulcis* Mill, var. *Ferragnes*)
15 orchard under reduced tillage (RT) as the habitual management practice during 14 years, we
16 studied the effect of four years implementation of two agricultural management practices on soil
17 aggregate distribution and associated OC. The implemented practices were reduced tillage with a
18 mix of *Vicia sativa* L. and *Avena sativa* L. as green manure (RTG) and no-tillage (NT). Four aggregate
19 size classes were differentiated by wet sieving (large- and small-macroaggregates, microaggregates,
20 and the silt plus clay fraction), and the microaggregates occluded into small macroaggregates
21 (SMm) were isolated. In addition, three C fractions were separated, using a density fractionation
22 method, within the small macroaggregates and microaggregates: the free light fraction (free LF-C),
23 intra-aggregate particulate OM (iPOM-C), and mineral fraction (mineral-C). The results showed that

24 the combination of reduced tillage plus green manure (RTG) was the most-efficient SLM practice for
25 SOC sequestration. The total SOC increased by about 14% in the surface layer when compared to
26 RT. Furthermore, green manure offset the effect of tillage on soil aggregate rupture. The plant
27 debris inputs from green manure and its incorporation into the soil by reduced tillage promoted
28 new aggregates formation and activated the subsequent physical-chemical protection of OC, mainly
29 the fine iPOM-C occluded in microaggregates and mineral-C fractions occluded within small
30 macroaggregates. Both C fractions together represented about 30% of the total OC accumulated in
31 the bulk soil. The cessation of tillage showed a trend to reduce CO₂ emissions, as it can be deduced
32 from the C higher concentration of organic C associated to the mineral particles and the particulate
33 organic matter occluded within microaggregates in the surface layer and the mineral-C occluded
34 within soil aggregates at 5-15 cm depth, but four years of cessation of tillage was not enough to
35 significantly increase the total OC in the bulk soil.

36 Key words: rain-fed almond orchard, sustainable land management, semiarid agroecosystems, soil
37 organic carbon fractionation, carbon sequestration.

38 **1. Introduction**

39 Agriculture plays a major role in the global fluxes of carbon dioxide and has been promoted as a
40 partial means for slowing further increases in greenhouse gases (GHG) through the potential for
41 soil C sequestration in cropping systems under suitable management practices (Robertson et al.,
42 2000). In the last decade, there has been an increasing policy interest in reducing GHG
43 emissions from agriculture (European Commission, 2008; UNFCCC, 2008). Policy makers face a
44 challenge to develop and implement effective GHG abatement strategies for agriculture, which
45 requires identifying the best management practices for each agro-ecosystem. In particular,

46 there is a need for a better knowledge of the effects of different agricultural practices on C
47 sequestration and on the mechanisms of C stabilization (Six et al., 2002; De Gryze et al. 2004),
48 particularly in semiarid areas and under rainfed agriculture.

49 The amount of plant residues and the degree of SOM decomposition are vital factors in the
50 formation and stabilization of aggregates, which in turn improves soil structure and drives soil
51 organic carbon (SOC) sequestration (Haynes and Beare, 1996). However, the mechanisms of
52 interaction between the soil structure and SOC dynamics are still not well understood (Blanco-
53 Canqui and Lal, 2004). It is known that agricultural management practices modify the soil
54 structure, with subsequent profound impacts on soil carbon (C) sequestration. In agricultural
55 soils, tillage and traffic operations are major factors involved in soil structure degradation, due
56 to aggregate disruption, with the loss of aggregate-occluded SOM through fragmentation and
57 compaction processes (Paustian et al., 1997a). In fact, the negative effects of conventional
58 tillage (CT) and the benefits of using conservation agriculture measures (such as crop rotations,
59 reduced tillage, cover crops, and no tillage), in terms of SOC sequestration, as well as suitable
60 techniques for greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation, have been demonstrated widely (Paustian et
61 al., 1997b; Abdalla et al., 2014).

62 No tillage (NT) is one of the conservation agriculture measures that have been applied in the
63 last three decades all over the world (Dimassi et al., 2014), however, contradictory results have
64 been obtained in relation to the utility of this technique from the point of view of C sequestration
65 (Powlson et al., 2014; Du et al., 2015). Green manure incorporation has also been demonstrated to
66 improve the soil structure and increase SOC accumulation, besides helping to control erosion
67 (Higashi et al., 2014). Nevertheless, it is not a common practice in semiarid agroecosystems

68 because of a fear of competition over water resources between the green manure and the main
69 crop (Almagro et al., 2013). Most of the experimental studies focused on the impacts of agriculture
70 management practices on SOC dynamics have been performed under extensive cereal and irrigated
71 crops in temperate (Virto et al., 2012; Dimassi et al., 2014); and Mediterranean areas (Álvaro-
72 Fuentes et al., 2009; Macinelli et al., 2010; ; López-Garrido et al., 2014). However, very few studies
73 have been carried out under rainfed tree crops in semiarid areas - where these crops represent a
74 significant proportion of the total agricultural production (Nieto et al., 2012; Almagro et al., 2013).
75 Moreover, only few of the above mentioned studies were orientated to determine the effects of
76 the conservation agriculture practices on SOC pools and on the way in which the OC interacts
77 physically and chemically with aggregates and the mineral particles. In fact, the physical protection
78 of SOM by aggregates (Denef et al., 2001; 2007) and the physical-chemical stabilization through the
79 adsorption and chemical binding of OC onto mineral surfaces are considered to be important
80 mechanisms of soil C stabilization (Krull et al., 2003; Marschner et al., 2008; Garcia-Franco et al.,
81 2014). The study of different SOM fractions within soil aggregates (free light fraction, intra-
82 aggregate particulate OM and OC associated with the mineral soil fraction) is a key element to
83 reliably assessing soil C dynamics and can be used as an early indicator of soil changes by
84 management practices (Six et al., 2002). The identification of those fractions will improve our
85 understanding of how aggregates stabilize and store SOC (von Lützow et al. 2007; Due et al. 2015),
86 helping us to select the best SLM practices with regard to the enhancement of SOC sequestration in
87 Mediterranean areas. In this study we evaluate the effects of three SLM practices on OC
88 stabilization by soil aggregates in an organic rainfed almond (*Prunus dulcis* Mill, var. Ferragnes)
89 orchard under Mediterranean semiarid conditions. This crop was selected since it is one of the
90 most widespread in these environmental conditions. Our hypotheses were: i) Green manure
91 increases plant residues and hence OC associated in soil aggregates, ii) the cessation of tillage

92 reduces soil aggregate disruption and increases physical protection of SOC, and iii) physical-
93 chemical protection is the main mechanism responsible of the accumulation of OC in these
94 agroecosystems. The general aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of different SLM
95 practices for C sequestration in order to promote changes in the semiarid agronomic systems
96 leading to the adaptation and mitigation of climate change. The specific objectives were: 1) to
97 establish the effects of reduced tillage, no-tillage and green manure on soil aggregation and OC
98 pools associated with aggregate-size classes, and 2) to increase in the knowledge of C sequestration
99 mechanisms in semiarid agroecosystems, in function of the management practices.

100 **2. Material and methods**

101 2.1. Site description and experimental design

102 The experimental area was established on 21 October 2008 in an organic, rain-fed almond
103 (*Prunus dulcis* Mill., var. Ferragnes) orchard located in Cehegín, in the Northwest of the province of
104 Murcia, in Southeast Spain (38° 3' 15" N, 1° 46' 12" W). The altitude of the orchard is 633 m.a.s.l.
105 and the average slope is lower than 7%. The climate is semiarid Mediterranean with an average
106 annual precipitation of 370 mm, concentrated in the spring and autumn months, but with great
107 inter- and intra-annual variability. The mean annual temperature is relatively high, 16.6 °C, and the
108 mean potential evapotranspiration reaches 800 mm year⁻¹, so the mean annual water deficit,
109 calculated by the Thornthwaite method, is 430 mm. July and August are the driest months. These
110 conditions result in aridic soil moisture content and a thermic soil temperature regime. The soil is a
111 *Petrocalcic Calcisol* (WRB, 2006) with the following main properties for the 0-30 cm soil layer: pH
112 (H₂O, 1: 5): 8.8 ± 0.2; electrical conductivity (1:5): 168.3 ± 23.3 μScm⁻¹; carbonates percentage:
113 54.2± 11.5%; calcium exchangeable percentage: 18.9 ± 0.2 %; sand (2000–50 μm), silt (50–2 μm),

114 and clay (<2 μm) contents: $430 \pm 120 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$, $415 \pm 90 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$, and $155 \pm 42 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$, respectively; and a
115 mixed-clay mineralogy dominated by kaolinite (1:1 layer type) and illite (2:1 layer type).

116 For 14 years (plantation age), the habitual soil management in the study area was reduced
117 tillage (RT) to control weeds. In 2008, two different SLM practices were applied: i) reduced tillage
118 plus green manure (RTG) and ii) no-tillage (NT). The experimental design consisted of nine plots in a
119 randomized-block design, with three replicates for each treatment. The plot dimensions were:
120 length 49 m and width 7 m. Each plot comprised seven almond trees: the five central trees were
121 used for all plant and soil measurements and the other two trees constituted guard rows (buffer
122 zone to avoid edge effects). In each plot, these 5 target trees also had two “guard rows” on the
123 sides (one at each side). The tillage affected the whole plot area, including the area around the
124 trunk base. The tillage affected the whole plot area, including the area around the trunk base. The
125 tillage consisted of chisel ploughing to 0.15 m depth using a cultivator, twice a year (autumn/spring)
126 to control weeds. The green manure consisted of a mix of common vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.) and
127 common oat (*Avena sativa* L.) in a proportion of 3:1, applied annually during early autumn at 150 kg
128 seeds ha^{-1} and cut off in May. After cutting, it was incorporated into the soil using a cultivator. In
129 the NT treatment, the weeds were cut manually in May and left on the soil surface. No addition of
130 OM or manure was performed.

131 2.2. Soil sampling and analysis

132 Soil samples were taken from three soil layers (0–5, 5–15, and 15–30 cm) in October 2012,
133 following crop harvest. The soils were sampled in the rows between the trees, 3.5 m away from the
134 tree trunk. Five disturbed soil samples were taken in each treatment, per block and depth, and

135 pooled to make two composite samples in each treatment, per block and depth (2 x 3 x 3 x 3). A
136 total of 54 composite samples were taken to the laboratory for further analysis.

137 2.2.1. Determination of soil properties

138 The soil samples were air-dried, sieved to <2 mm, and analyzed in the laboratory, in
139 triplicate. The soil carbonate content was determined using a Bernard Calcimeter, exchangeable
140 calcium (Ca²⁺) was measured by the method of Duchaufour (1975), and the pH (1:5 soil: water) was
141 determined with a pH meter (CRISON 20). The soil electrical conductivity (EC) was measured for the
142 same suspension, using an EC meter. The textural characteristics were determined using a Coulter
143 LS200 'Laser particle sizer'. Mineralogical analysis of the clay particles was performed by X-Ray
144 diffractometry, using a Philips PW 1710 model (Philips, Eindhoven, Holland). Microbial C was
145 measured with a respirometer (MicroTrack 4200-Sy Lab, Madrid, Spain) and calculated according to
146 Anderson and Domsch (1978).

147 2.2.2. Separation of water-stable soil aggregates

148 Aggregate-size separation was carried out on each sample using a modified wet sieving
149 method adapted from Elliott (1986). Briefly, a 100-g sample of air-dried soil (5-mm sieved) was
150 placed on top of a 2000- μ m sieve and submerged for 5 min in deionized water at room
151 temperature. The sieving was done manually by moving the sieve up and down 3 cm, 50 times in 2
152 min, to achieve aggregate separation. A series of three sieves (2000, 250, and 63 μ m) was used to
153 obtain four aggregate classes: i) > 2000 μ m (large macroaggregates; LM), ii) 250 to 2000 μ m (small
154 macroaggregates; SM), iii) 63 to 250 μ m (microaggregates; m), and iv) < 63 μ m (silt plus clay-sized
155 particles; s+c). The aggregate-size classes were oven dried (50°C), weighed, and stored in glass jars
156 at room temperature (21°C) (Figure 1A). Protected microaggregates contained within

157 macroaggregates (large and small) were obtained to carry out the microaggregate isolation
158 procedure described by Six et al. (2000) and Deneff et al. (2004). Briefly, a 10-g of macroaggregate
159 subsample was immersed in deionized water on top of a 250- μm mesh screen inside a cylinder. The
160 small macroaggregates were shaken together with 50 glass beads (4 mm diameter) until complete
161 macroaggregates disruption was observed. Once the macroaggregates had been broken up,
162 microaggregates and other <250 μm material passed through the mesh screen with the help of a
163 continuous water flow to the sieve. The material retained on the 63- μm sieve was wet sieved, to
164 ensure that the isolated microaggregates were water stable (Six et al., 2000). These
165 microaggregates obtained from macroaggregates were oven-dried, at 50°C (24 h) in aluminium
166 trays, and weighed (Figure 1B).

167 2.2.3. OC fractionation by density

168 Due to the very low proportion of microaggregates within large macroaggregates obtained
169 in the previous procedure, the subsequent OC fractionation by density was only performed on the
170 small macroaggregates (250-2000 μm) and microaggregates (63-250 μm). The density fractionation
171 was performed using sodium polytungstate (SPT) at a density of 1.6 g cm^{-3} . A subsample (10 g) of
172 oven-dried material was put into a 50-ml centrifuge tube together with 35 ml of SPT. Briefly, the
173 free light fraction (free LF) was isolated by density flotation. The liquid was gently stirred - to avoid
174 breaking up the aggregates - and the floating material (free LF) was aspirated, filtered using a 20-
175 μm nylon filter, rinsed with distilled water, transferred into aluminium tins, and dried at 50°C. The
176 remaining material, the heavy fraction (HF: iPOM+sand), in the centrifuge tube was washed with
177 distilled water and then centrifuged. The heavy fraction was then dispersed in 5 g l^{-1} sodium
178 hexametaphosphate. After shaking for 18 h, the dispersed heavy fraction was passed through
179 2000-, 250-, and 63- μm sieves, depending on the aggregate size being analyzed (Álvaro-Fuentes et

180 al., 2009). The intra-aggregate (iPOM) material and sand retained on the sieves - coarse iPOM (250-
181 2000 μm) and fine iPOM (63-250 μm) - and the material passing through the 63- μm sieve (mineral
182 particles) were allowed to settle, centrifuged (3000 rpm, 20 min), and oven-dried at 60°C before
183 samples were weighed and ground (Schwendenmann and Pendall, 2006) (Figure 1C).

184 2.2.4. Carbon and nitrogen determinations

185 The soil organic C and total N concentrations were determined in the bulk soil and
186 separately for water-stable aggregates, micro within macroaggregates and density fractions using
187 an Elemental Analyzer (LECO TRUSPEC CN, Michigan, USA) after carbonates removal by 2M HCl. The
188 samples were analyzed in triplicate.

189 The OC concentration within each water-stable aggregates size, micro within
190 macroaggregates and density fractions were expressed on a sand-free aggregate basis. The OC
191 content in the density fractions were also expressed as a soil basis multiplying the fraction's C
192 concentration by the weight proportion of that fraction:

$$193 \quad \text{OC content (g C/kg}_{\text{soil}}) = (\text{OC})_{\text{fraction}} * (\text{density pool proportion})_{\text{soil}}$$

194 Where $(\text{OC})_{\text{fraction}}$ is the organic carbon concentration in each density fraction; and $(\text{density pool}$
195 $\text{proportion})_{\text{soil}}$ is the proportion (in percentage) of each density fraction to the bulk soil.

196 2.3. Statistical analyses

197 To compare the effects of treatments and soil depths a GLM procedure was carried out
198 which considered treatment and depth as fixed factors and block as a random variable. When
199 significant, differences among treatments and depths were identified at the 0.05 probability level of
200 significance using Tukey's test. Prior to the analyses, the data were examined for normality by the

201 Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and for homogeneity of variances by the Levene’s test. Data that were
202 not distributed normally (coarse iPOM-C, fine iPOM-C and mineral-C from small macroaggregates)
203 were ln-transformed. Pearson correlation analysis was applied in order to explore the relationships
204 between all the study variables within treatments across depths. All analyses were carried out using
205 IBM SPSS statistics 19.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois).

206 **3. Results**

207 3.1. SOC, C/N ratio and microbial C in the bulk soil

208 The SOC concentration in the bulk soil was significantly greater in RTG than in RT or NT at 0-
209 5 cm depth, while no differences were observed among treatments below 5 cm depth (Table 1). In
210 all treatments, slightly higher values of SOC were found at the surface compared to deeper layers,
211 but no significant differences were found between depths within treatments. The C/N ratio
212 oscillated between 9.6 and 12.1, depending on the treatment and depth, and did not differ among
213 treatments or depths, although slightly higher values were obtained in RTG and NT with respect to
214 RT.

215 The soil microbial C was significantly higher in RTG than in RT or NT at 0-5 cm (Table 1).
216 While we did not detect differences between treatments at 5-15 cm depth, below 15 cm both
217 tillage treatments (RTG and RT) showed higher microbial C than NT.

218 219 3.2. Aggregate-size distribution and associated organic carbon

220 3.2.1. Water-stable aggregates

221 The main differences in the aggregate-size distribution among treatments were observed at
222 the plough layer (0-15 cm). RT and RTG contained about 30% lower LM (> 2000 μm) than NT, while
223 RTG and NT showed about 40% more SM (250-2000 μm) than RT at 0-5 cm depth (Figure 2a). At 5-
224 15 cm depth, no differences in the proportion of LM were observed among treatments but the SM
225 proportion was higher in RTG than in RT and NT (Figure 2b). Interestingly, both tillage treatments
226 (RT and RTG) exhibit an increase in the percentage of macroaggregates (LM and SM in RT and LM in
227 RTG) from the 0-5cm to the 5-15 cm layer, while no differences were observed in NT soil profile.

228 The proportion of microaggregates (63-250 μm) was similar than that of macroaggregates
229 (LM or SM) at surface and slightly higher below this layer in all treatments. At 0-5 cm RTG showed
230 higher proportion of m (250-63 μm) compared to RT and NT, while both tillage treatments (RT and
231 RTG) contained about 30% higher proportion of microaggregates than NT at 5-15 cm (Figure 2b).

232 Silt plus clay-sized particles were the most abundant in all treatments at 0-5 cm depth
233 representing 48, 46 and 41% for RT, RTG and NT, respectively. From 0-5 to 5-15 cm depth, the
234 percentage of these particles significantly decreased in the tillage treatments (RT and RTG), while
235 no change was observed in NT.

236 3.2.2. Microaggregates within small macroaggregates

237 The percentage of microaggregates within small macroaggregates (SMm) was relatively low
238 in these soils and ranged between 5% and 12%, depending on the treatment and depth (Table 2).
239 RTG was the treatment with the highest percentage of SMm and associated OC (OC-SMm), at all
240 depths, compared to RT and NT.

241 The conversion from RT to RTG led to an increase in the percentage of SMm at 0-5 cm depth
242 of about 120%, and 40% below this layer. In addition, the OC associated to SMm was slightly higher
243 (about 30%) in RTG compared to RT at the plow layer (Table 2).

244 Conversion from RT to NT lead to an increase of 32% in the percentage of SMm at the
245 surface layer and a decrease of 19% at 5-15 cm depth while no differences were observed below
246 the plow layer. SMm-OC concentration was slightly higher in RT compared to NT at the whole soil
247 profile but not significant differences were obtained between them (Table 2).

248

249 3.2.3. Changes in OC associated to aggregate-size fractions

250 A significant increase in total SOC was found in RTG compared to RT and NT at the surface
251 layer (Table 1). The highest OC concentration was found in s+c for all the treatments and depths,
252 although no significant differences were found between treatments (Figure 3). The organic C
253 associated to s+c represented between 44% and 58.5% of the total SOC at 0-5 cm depth and
254 between 33 and 45% at deeper layers, depending on the treatment (Table 3). On the contrary, the
255 concentration of OC within large macroaggregates was very low (lower than 3%; Figure 3)
256 representing the lowest percentage of the total SOC in all treatments. Over the whole profile,
257 higher concentrations of OC associated with macroaggregates (large and small) and
258 microaggregates were observed under treatment RTG than under RT or NT, these differences being
259 more accentuated at the surface than in the deepest layer (Figure 3). Thus, the conversion from RT
260 to RTG led to an increase of 27% in the OC content in total macroaggregates and of 19% in the OC
261 content associated with microaggregates, at the surface layer (Figure 3a). The conversion from RT

262 to NT did not caused significant changes in the distribution of OC concentration through
263 aggregates.

264 The OC associated to large macroaggregates decreased with depth in tillage treatments
265 while no change was observed in NT through the soil profile. However, the OC concentration in the
266 small macroaggregates did not change through the soil profile in RTG while in RT and NT the
267 highest OC concentration in the small-macroaggregates was observed at 5-15 cm depth (Figure 3 a
268 and b).

269 3.2.4. Changes in organic carbon in density fractions

270 The OC associated with the free light fraction (free LF-C) represented between 3% and 11%
271 of the total SOC, according to the treatment and depth (Table 3). At the soil surface, the free LF-C
272 content was 1.5-times higher in treatment RTG than in RT and NT. However, below 5 cm no
273 differences were found between treatments RT and RTG and both had more than twice free LF-C
274 than NT treatment (Table 3). Moreover, the tillage treatments (RT and RTG) showed a significant
275 increase in the free LF-C pool from the 0-5 to 5-15 cm layer while no change with depth was
276 observed in NT.

277 The total iPOM-C represented higher percentages of the total SOC in RTG and NT (about
278 20%) than in treatment RT (about 12%), in the whole soil profile (Table 3). Differences in the total
279 iPOM-C content between treatments were mainly observed at the surface layer with higher
280 contents in RTG (114%) and NT (33%) compared to RT (Table 3). Fine iPOM-C occluded in
281 microaggregates was the main responsible fraction of the gains in total iPOM-C in RTG and NT
282 respect to RT at this layer (Figure 4a). While a significant decrease in total iPOM-C with depth was
283 observed in RTG, not change with depth was observed in RT and NT in this pool (Table 3). The total

284 occluded mineral-C represented 23-34% of the total SOC, depending on the treatment and depth.
285 Differences in this C pool among treatments were only observed at the 0-5 cm depth - where RTG
286 showed the highest values, followed by RT and NT (Table 3). Mineral-C within SM was the fraction
287 mainly responsible for the gains in total occluded mineral-C in RTG, compared to RT, in the plow
288 layer. Furthermore, the OC concentration in mineral-C within SM was higher in NT than in RT at the
289 plough layer (0-15 cm) (Figure 4a and b).

290 The highest concentration of mineral-C in microaggregates was observed in RT at the
291 surface while at 5-15 cm higher concentration in NT and RTG respect to RT was observed (Figure
292 4b). Below the plough layer RTG showed the highest concentrations of mineral-C in
293 microaggregates compared to RT or NT (Figure 4c).

294 **4. Discussion**

295 4.1. Impact of management practices on soil aggregation

296 As mentioned earlier, previous to the establishment of the experiment these fields had been
297 plowed for 14 years (RT treatment). After four years from the implementation of the tested
298 agricultural practices: green manure plantation (RTG) and tillage cessation (NT), our results showed
299 the following changes in the plow layer: (i) an increase in total macroaggregates in RTG and NT
300 compared to RT; and (ii) an increase in microaggregates, free and occluded within
301 macroaggregates, in RTG compared to RT and NT. These results proved that tillage cessation lead to
302 an improvement of the soil macro-structure. However, the green manure plantation not only
303 offsets the effect of tillage on macro-structure, but also improves the soil micro-structure.

304 It is well known that tillage promotes the breakdown of soil macroaggregates into
305 microaggregates and silt-plus clay-sized particles, ultimately affecting soil aggregate stability and its
306 distribution and enhancing OC mineralization in macroaggregates (Denef et al., 2001). Higher
307 percentage of silt-plus-clay sized particles and lower percentages of LM, at the surface layer,
308 together with the significant decrease of silt plus clay with depth in the tillage treatments,
309 compared to no tillage (NT) (Figure 2) was observed in our soils which might be an indicator of the
310 lower macroaggregate stability of tillage soils compared to NT (Figure 2). Other authors have
311 obtained, at the surface, a significant increase in silt plus clay-particles in tillage treatments
312 (included reduced tillage), compared to no tillage treatments (Andruschkewitsch et al., 2014).
313 However, the incorporation of green manure enhanced the formation of new aggregates in the
314 surface layer in RTG. Thus, while in RT, the large and small macroaggregates percentages were
315 reduced significantly, in RTG large macroaggregates were significantly reduced but small
316 macroaggregates did not change at 0-5 cm and increase in 5-15 cm layer, compared to NT (Figure
317 2). Other authors obtained a high proportion of macroaggregates after the addition of fresh organic
318 residue (Olchin et al., 2008; Yan et al., 2012). The higher aboveground biomass values in RTG than
319 in RT (182 g m⁻² and 114 g m⁻², respectively; Almagro et al., 2013), together with the higher C
320 concentration of the free-LF fraction (an indicator of the input of plant material) and microbial C in
321 the surface layer, relative to RT, were key factors promoting the processes involved in soil
322 aggregation, as has been suggested by other authors (Denef et al., 2001; Abiven et al., 2007). In
323 addition, the relatively rapid decomposition rates of green manure observed in an adjacent field
324 (Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2014) might favor the soil aggregate formation in RTG. Other
325 authors (Martens et al., 2000; Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2004) have demonstrated rapid aggregation
326 (after 84 days of incubation) in soils with high contents of common oat (*A. sativa*) and increases of
327 soil aggregation and OC concentration due to the residues of legumes, which are often rich in the

328 labile organic fraction and nitrogen content (Palm et al., 2014). The input into the soil of fresh
329 organic material from green manure, in RTG, involves an important increase of binding agents, such
330 as polysaccharides and root exudates, promoting the formation of soil aggregates. Several authors
331 have proven the effect of labile organic C fractions as aggregate-stabilizing agents, which improve
332 macroaggregate formation (Degens, 1997). Our results indicate the important role of the quantity
333 and quality of the plant material input in the stimulation of the soil microbiota, in relation to the
334 production of binding agents that increase aggregates formation and stabilization - as has been
335 reported by other authors (Abiven et al., 2007; Tang et al., 2011).

336 RTG management increased not only the percentage of small macroaggregates but also the
337 percentage of free microaggregates and microaggregates occluded inside the macroaggregates.
338 This formation of microaggregates might be attributed to the increase of decomposed organic
339 matter, biogenic products and other binding agents due to the green manure, which promoted the
340 solid-phase reaction between organic matter and clay and silt particles - leading to the formation of
341 stable microaggregates (Golchin et al., 1994). The aggregation of organo-mineral particles leading
342 to microaggregates formation was driven by the soil-ecosystem characteristics of these areas. The
343 mechanism of organo-mineral association can be mainly attributed to the presence of multivalent
344 cations and mineral surfaces capable of absorbing organic materials in the soil matrix. In our study
345 area, the high proportion of Ca^{2+} cations and minerals with high specific surface area (mainly the
346 inter-stratified illite-montmorillonite) in the soil matrix promoted the formation of organo-mineral
347 microaggregates. These stabilization mechanisms are usual in Mediterranean areas and have been
348 found in other sites, close to the study area (Garcia-Franco et al., 2014). Overall, the results
349 concerning the effect of RTG implementation on soil structure suggest: a) in a first stage following
350 green manure plantation the fresh organic inputs quickly induced the formation of

351 macroaggregates due to increase in binding agents; and b) in a second stage, the characteristics of
352 the soil matrix promoted the reaction between organic matter and clay and silt particles - leading to
353 the formation of microaggregates. An important proportion of these new microaggregates were
354 formed within the macroaggregates.

355

356 4.2. Changes in SOC dynamics with management practices

357 The identification of the best management practices, in order to regulate the CO₂ fluxes in
358 agroecosystems, is a key aspect in the adaptation of agriculture to climate change. In this
359 experiment, four years after the conversion from RT to RTG an increase of about 16 % in total SOC
360 was found at the surface layer (0-5 cm), while no change was observed after the conversion of RT
361 to NT (Table 1). The changes in the organic C pools, after the treatments, occurred mainly in the
362 surface layer (0-5 cm), slight partial changes were detected at 5-15 cm depth, and no changes were
363 observed at deeper. Likewise, other studies showed that the changes in soil C stocks following land
364 use or management changes occur mainly in the topsoil (De Gryze et al., 2004).

365 The organic C gained in RTG relative to RT was distributed among the aggregate-size
366 fractions showing significant differences in large macroaggregates and microaggregates and
367 marginal differences in small macroaggregates and silt plus clay fractions. Although in percentage,
368 the highest increment occurred in the OC associated with the large macroaggregates, due to the
369 very low OC concentration in this aggregate-size, this increment was not significant of the total OC
370 increase in the study period. The main increments were accumulated in free and occluded
371 microaggregates within small macroaggregates, which is a key aspect in term of C sequestration
372 (Figure 3).

373 Higher OC concentration in the free microaggregates under RTG, compared with RT was
374 observed which is beneficial to SOC sequestration in the long-term because microaggregates have a
375 longer turnover time and higher stability than macroaggregates (Denef et al., 2007; Huang et al.,
376 2010). In addition, the green manure also increased the OC content of the microaggregates within
377 small macroaggregates, this gain being about 30% at the plough layer with respect to RT.

378 Previous works have highlighted the importance, of the incorporation of plant residues by
379 tillage (rather than leaving them on the surface), which could be a result of better contact with soil
380 particles and soil microbes - hence improving the physico-chemical protection of SOC (Christopher
381 et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2012). In fact, there were significantly positive correlations between the
382 percentage of small macroaggregates and the C concentration of the free light fraction (an indicator
383 of plant material inputs) in both RTG ($r= 0.76$, $p<0.01$) and RT ($r= 0.45$, $p<0.05$) treatments, while no
384 correlations were found in NT. This highlights the key role of the incorporation of plant material
385 into the soil in stimulating the formation of small macroaggregates, which in turns enhances the
386 protection of OC in the microaggregates formed within small macroaggregates - as it has been
387 previously reported by other authors (Oades, 1984; Golchin et al., 1994). Indeed, the higher
388 concentration of OC in the microaggregates within small macroaggregates in RTG compared to RT
389 indicates the potential of this management practice in promoting SOC stabilization.

390 The shift from RT to NT did not enhance neither the OC concentration in the bulk soil, nor
391 the total OC concentration in any of the aggregate size at any depth. In addition, at the surface
392 layer, a decoupling between the percentage of SMm and the associated OC was observed in NT,
393 with a higher proportion of microaggregates within small macroaggregates but lower OC-SMm
394 concentration, compared to RT. Other authors (West and Post, 2002; Denef et al., 2007) did not
395 find increases in the OC associated with microaggregates within-macroaggregates or changes in the

396 total SOC levels when NT was compared with conventional tillage, in semiarid agroecosystems and
397 under different crops (mainly cereals), in the short-term (after five years of tillage cessation). By
398 contrast, Plaza-Bonilla et al. (2013), in longer-term experiments, found an increase in the
399 proportion of macroaggregates and an enrichment of the C concentration within microaggregates
400 under NT compared to conventional tillage. It is well known that the accumulation of SOC under NT
401 is a slow and gradual process (Denef et al., 2007).

402 At 5-15 cm depth, the proportion of SMm and OC SMm was greater in RT than in NT,
403 supporting the positive effect of tillage on OC migration through the soil profile, as commented
404 before. In this sense, it is interesting to point out that in a previous study, we detected much higher
405 bulk density and shear strength of the soil profile in NT compared to tillage treatments (Martínez-
406 Mena et al., 2013), which might help to inhibit the migration of the OC through the soil profile,
407 slowing down its incorporation into the soil (Bronick and Lal, 2005). Indeed, the soil compaction in
408 this treatment might limit the oxygen content and restrict the access to the subsoil of
409 microorganisms (De Gryze et al., 2005). The greater reduction of the microbial C below the plow
410 layer (15-30 cm) in NT (ratio microbial-C at 0-5/ microbial-C at 15-30: 3.31) compared to the tillage
411 treatments (ratio microbial-C at 0-5/ microbial-C at 15-30: 2.28 and 2.82 for RT and RTG,
412 respectively) supports this idea. In fact, other authors reported higher biological activity and greater
413 accumulation of microbial-C at the surface under NT treatments (Balesdent et al., 2000). The lack
414 of correlation found in NT between the plant biomass input (as free LF-C) and small
415 macroaggregate formation is consistent with this hypothesis.

416 4.3. Changes in OC associated with density fractions

417 The significant increase in iPOM in RTG compared to RT, coupled to the increase of
418 microaggregates within macroaggregates, suggests a hierarchical model for the physical protection
419 and stabilization of the organic C in the soil with RTG management. In this model macroaggregates
420 were the nucleus for microaggregate formation in the center of macroaggregates (Oades, 1984).
421 Similar to previously described models (Six et al., 2004), we suggest that in a first stage following
422 green manure plantation the new litter inputs quickly induced the formation of macroaggregates
423 due to an increase of binding agents like polysaccharides (Díaz et al., 1994; Golchin et al., 1994). In
424 a second stage, inside these macroaggregates, the characteristics of soil matrix (as indicated above)
425 promoted the solid-phase reaction between organic matter and clay and silt particles - leading to
426 the formation of stable microaggregates (Edwards and Bremner, 1967). During the formation of
427 the microaggregates the fine particulate organic matter present in the soil matrix, coming from the
428 green manure litter, is occluded and long-term sequestered in these microaggregates.

429 This proposed hierarchical model for C sequestration in RTG, is supported by the strongly
430 positive correlation between the OC associated with the total intra-aggregate particulate organic
431 matter (total iPOM-C) and the microbial C ($r=0.705$, $p<0.01$). This suggests that iPOM-C might be a C
432 source for the microorganisms which are also inductors of the microaggregates within
433 macroaggregates formation (Courtier-Murias et al., 2013). Moreover, in RTG, the occlusion of fine
434 iPOM-C within small macroaggregates in the surface layer was, although not significant, slightly
435 greater than in RT.

436 Similar results were obtained by other authors (Álvaro-Fuentes et al., 2009; Trigalet et al.,
437 2014), suggesting that a significant part of the C stabilization in SM is due to the physical-chemical
438 protection of SOM by mineral particles (Krull et al., 2003; Bronick and Lal, 2005). In fact, when the
439 fresh organic matter was added in the RTG treatment, a positive correlation ($r=0.656$, $p<0.05$)

440 between the free-LF-C and total mineral-C (from SM and m) was obtained, indicating that a relevant
441 proportion of the fresh and labile OC, as free LF-C, was absorbed by mineral particles favouring its
442 stabilization. Probably, the mechanical effect of tillage led to the fragmentation of coarse iPOM-C
443 and so to the lack of significant differences between RTG and RT in this fraction in the short-term.
444 In RT, the fresh litter input was not enough to offset the loss of coarse iPOM-C due to the tillage.

445 In the surface layer, the fine iPOM-C within small macroaggregates was also slightly greater
446 in treatment NT than in RT. Similar results were reported by other authors when conventional
447 tillage was shifted to no tillage in long-term experiments (Six et al., 1998; Álvaro-Fuentes et al.,
448 2009). In addition, the soil C concentration ratio of fine iPOM to coarse iPOM inside small-
449 macroaggregates (as a relative measure of macroaggregate turnover; Six et al., 2000) was
450 significant higher in RTG and NT than in RT at 0-5 cm depth (Figure 5) indicating that the addition of
451 green manure or the cessation of tillage decreased the turnover rates of small macroaggregates in
452 the top soil promoting C sequestration. The fact that NT at surface had higher proportion of
453 microaggregates within small macroaggregates than RT while at 5-15 cm depth the opposite occurs
454 is consistent with the ratios fine iPOM-C/coarse iPOM-C at both depths and validate the theory
455 given by Six et al., 2000 about the increased formation of micro within macroaggregates due to the
456 absence of macroaggregates disruption.

457 Irrespective of the tillage and/or green manure, higher contents of mineral-C, compared
458 with the free or intra-aggregate particulate OC pools, in our soils, indicate a high capacity for
459 organic C stabilization through organo-mineral complexes formation, being less susceptible to
460 mineralization (Courtier-Murias et al., 2013; Trigalet et al., 2014).

461 Nevertheless, and despite the fact that the greatest storage of C in these soils occurs in the
462 mineral-C pool, a significant part (17-25%, depending on the treatment and depth) occurs in the

463 intra-aggregate POM fraction. In particular, the fine iPOM-C in microaggregates was the fraction
464 which more differences between the alternative treatments (RTG and NT) and RT. These results
465 indicate that, in the former, new microaggregates could have been formed free in the soil, with the
466 incorporation of fine iPOM-C. This supports the idea that the incorporation of new C into free
467 microaggregates is an important factor contributing to C sequestration since the C contained in free
468 microaggregates has a slower turnover than that in macroaggregates (Denef et al., 2001).

469 **Conclusions**

470 Important changes in the dynamic of soil organic C were found following the
471 implementation of sustainable land management practices in a semiarid agro-ecosystem. The
472 integration of green manure and reduced tillage (RTG treatment) was shown as a good option for
473 climate change mitigation and adaptation due to the increase observed in soil C sequestration. A
474 double mechanism for C protection and stabilization in semiarid agricultural systems under RTG
475 management is proposed: i) physical protection of OC in microaggregates within new
476 macroaggregates, and ii) physico-chemical stabilization through the formation of organo-mineral
477 complexes. The minimum tillage associated in this treatment favors the incorporation of plant
478 material promoting the soil aggregation in deeper layers.

479 The cessation of tillage showed a trend to reduce CO₂ emissions, as it can be deduced from
480 the C higher concentration of organic C associated to the mineral particles and the particulate
481 organic matter occluded within microaggregates in the surface layer and the mineral-C occluded
482 within soil aggregates at 5-15 cm depth, but four years of cessation of tillage was not enough to
483 significantly increase the total OC in the bulk soil.

484 This study also emphasizes the interest of the fractionation of the organic C pools, according
485 turnover rates, in order to better understand SOC dynamics as affected by agricultural management
486 practices.

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624 Figure 1

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627 Figure 2

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Aggregate size class (μm)

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633 Figure 4

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642 Figure 5

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646 **Table 1.** The SOC, C/N ratio, and microbial carbon values of the bulk soil at three depths under distinct
 647 sustainable land management practices: RT (reduced tillage), RTG (reduced tillage with green manure), and
 648 NT (no tillage).

Soil properties	Depth (cm)	Soil management practices		
		RT	RTG	NT
OC Bulk soil (g kg ⁻¹)	0-5	11.8 ± 0.5bA	13.7 ± 0.6aA	10.2 ± 0.4bA
	5-15	11.1 ± 1.1aA	11.3 ± 1.6aA	9.7 ± 1.6aA
	15-30	11.1 ± 0.6aA	8.9 ± 0.6aA	8.8 ± 0.9aA
<u>C/N Ratio</u>	0-5	9.6 ± 0.7aA	11.56 ± 0.3aA	11.2 ± 1.8aA
	5-15	9.5 ± 0.8aA	11.6 ± 2.2aA	10.1 ± 0.8aA
	15-30	9.7 ± 2.1aA	8.4 ± 0.8aA	12.1 ± 1.8aA
Microbial C (mg kg ⁻¹)	0-5	1410.1 ± 207.5bA	2012.5 ± 194.8aA	1407.1 ± 185.4bA
	5-15	977.8 ± 131.5aB	1055.6 ± 152.7aAB	855.1 ± 125.3aAB
	15-30	618.3 ± 51.2aB	713.3 ± 51.2aB	425.9 ± 48.7bB

649 Numerical values are means ± standard errors. Different lowercase letters in rows indicate significant differences
 650 between treatments, at each depth, in some soil properties. Different uppercase letters in columns indicate significant
 651 differences between depths, within each treatment (Tukey's test, p < 0.05).

652

653 **Table 2.** Weight percentage and organic carbon concentration (g kg^{-1} aggregate) of the SMm
 654 (microaggregates within small macroaggregates) in the 0-5, 5-15, and 15-30 cm soil layers, under
 655 distinct sustainable land management practices (RT, reduced tillage; RTG, reduced tillage plus green-
 656 manure; NT, no-tillage).

Depth (cm)	Soil management practices		
	RT	RTG	NT
SMm			
0-5	4.96 ± 0.23cA	11.00 ± 0.41aA	6.55±0.19bA
5-15	7.98 ± 0.21bB	11.38 ± 0.40aA	6.46±0.34cA
15-30	8.45 ± 0.50bB	11.96 ± 0.29aA	8.60±0.71bB
OC –SMm			
0-5	15,37±0,83abA	19,08±1,85aA	11,46±1,43bA
5-15	14,02±0,22abA	18,49±1,63aA	12,47±2,85bA
15-30	14,12±1,06aA	15,50±2,24aA	10,91±1,78aA

657 Numerical values are means ± standard errors. Different lower-case letters in rows indicate significant
 658 differences between tillage treatments at each depth. Different upper-case letters in columns indicate
 659 significant differences between depths within each treatment (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).
 660

661 **Table 3.** The organic carbon concentration (g C kg⁻¹ soil) of free LF-C, total intra-aggregate particulate organic
 662 matter (iPOM-C within small-macroaggregates + iPOM-C within microaggregates), and total occluded
 663 mineral OC (mineral-C within small-macroaggregates + mineral-C within microaggregates) and total
 664 free mineral C in the 0-5, 5-15, and 15-30 cm soil layers, as affected by the treatments (RT, reduced
 665 tillage; RTG, reduced tillage plus green manure; NT, no tillage).

Soil management practices			
Depth (cm)	RT	RTG	NT
<u>Free LF-C</u>			
0-5	0.45 ± 0.02bB	0.71 ± 0.04aB	0.46 ± 0.01bA
5-15	1.21 ± 0.11aA	1.21 ± 0.12aA	0.53 ± 0.05bA
15-30	0.58 ± 0.07aB	0.58 ± 0.02aB	0.37 ± 0.05bA
<u>Total iPOM-C</u>			
0-5	1.36 ± 0.08cA	2.91 ± 0.11aA	1.81 ± 0.07bA
5-15	1.55 ± 0.07aA	2.20 ± 0.10aB	2.40 ± 0.72aA
15-30	1.52 ± 0.08aA	1.70 ± 0.13aC	1.64 ± 0.10aA
<u>Total occluded mineral-C</u>			
0-5	2.70 ± 0.13abA	3.20 ± 0.14aB	2.31 ± 0.14bB
5-15	3.07 ± 0.44aA	3.80 ± 0.23aA	3.34 ± 0.19aA
15-30	2.38 ± 0.14aA	2.94 ± 0.27aB	2.66 ± 0.10aB

666 Numerical values are means ± standard errors. Different lowercase letters in rows indicate significant
 667 differences between treatments at each depth. Different uppercase letters in columns indicate
 668 significant differences between depths within each treatment (Tukey's test, p <0.05).
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